

PILOT TESTS

In Real Port Environments

Valencia, Spain

📍 Valencia Port, Spain

Vol.5

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From Research to Innovative Results

To ensure close collaboration between the project end users (security agencies and port authorities) and the technical partners throughout the project lifecycle, SMAUG will showcase and validate the multiple solutions developed during the project in 3 pilots. These will be executed, and their outcomes will be evaluated in a real port environment, specifically at the ports of Valencia (Spain), Elefsina (Greece), Heraklion (Greece), and Drammen (Norway).

- Pilot Summary

Valencia Port

Our partners are sharing the collective insights and updates on the technical validations conducted so far regarding **Aerial and Underwater Detection**.

Figure: Hull scan sonar image

Underwater Detection in Valencia Port

Regarding underwater detection, a few technologies were tested in Valencia.

First, the hydrophone system was installed by UPM. A structure with three hydrophones was deployed on the seafloor in the Xità dock. The hydrophones were connected via cables to a Raspberry Pi through an audio interface located outside the water. The Raspberry Pi was responsible for connecting the system to the data broker. Both the hardware installation and the broker connection were successfully completed during the September tests. Next steps include testing the algorithm for cross-referencing AIS data with hydrophone data and the deployment of a new hydrophone system with 5G connectivity.

Figure: Hydrophones underwater structure

Figure: Hydrophone installation diagram

Furthermore, a sonar system carried by the LEMVOS USV was also tested. Initial trials focused on verifying the USV navigation and communication using the public network. Afterwards, a hull inspection test was conducted: a bottle was attached to a Spanish Customs vessel, and as shown in the last Figure, the bottle was clearly visible in the sonar image. The next steps focus on improving object detection with the sonar, installing the UUV on board the USV, and transmitting images from all cameras via the 5G network.

Figure: USV deployment

Figure: USV performing navigation tests

Figure: Bottle attached to patrol boat hull

Figure: Hull scan sonar image

Aerial Detection

Figure: Tethered UAV installed on the AEAT boat

Regarding aerial detection, the tethered drone system was installed at the port dock, where initial static flight tests were carried out. Afterwards, the same tethered system was mounted on the AEAT patrol boat. Flight tests were then performed on board the vessel, focusing on the detection of nearby vessels and floating objects at sea. The next steps include conducting new tests at higher speeds.

Figure: Tethered UAV detections

AI acquisition & Data integration

Regarding data acquisition, several actions were carried out to ensure proper integration and management of the information generated by the different systems.

The data management platform (including the Broker, API, RTSP server, and related components) was developed by FAVIT. The system was deployed on the port server, and the necessary services were prepared to support the use case. A data display interface was also set up to visualize the information received from each connected device.

The AIS system, implemented by ATHANOR, was installed at the port facility, and connected to the local area network (LAN). It was then integrated with FAVIT's data platform, followed by a functional test to validate the operation of the complete data chain.

The AI detection algorithms, developed by INDRA, were installed, and connected to their server within the port datacentre. Initial tests were conducted using data collected during the trials, and a performance evaluation of the detection algorithms was carried out to assess their effectiveness.

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